

Gefördert durch:

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

Introduce Impact-Pathways in a CRIS – support societal impact orientation in research projects and funding processes

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**Societal Impact of Research:
increasingly desired - challenging to assess**

SynSICRIS: What is new in this approach?

Record the information during project lifecycle
= replace parts of proposals and reports!

Focus on activities that increase the likelihood for societal impact

Monitoring-Tool

Criteria-Set

Criteria-Set

Reflexive and Responsible Research and Innovation Processes

How was the research process conducted to contribute to societal impact?

Contribution to Innovation Systems

Were innovations and solutions being developed, are they likely to be distributed and was innovation capability improved?

Contribution to Sustainable Development

Can an application of the project results contribute to reaching sustainability goals?

Syn**SI**CRIS – Synergies for Societal Impact in CRIS

Monitoring-Tool

+

Additional entities
related to societal
impact creation

Additional Functions

- Impact strategies
- Funding processes

Impact Pathway – structure items in an intervention logic

Impact Pathway - part of the data model

Research & Interactions

2. Level to connect objectives and activities

Every box is an item of an entity

The screenshot shows a grid of boxes representing different stages of an impact pathway. The columns are labeled: 1 Background, 2 Research and development objectives, 3 Interactions with partners and stakeholders. Outputs for dissemination, 4 Application (opportunities), 5 Expected Societal Impact, and 6 Contribution to funding programme objectives. Each box contains a title and a brief description, with arrows indicating connections between them.

This screenshot shows a form titled "3 Interactions with partners and stakeholders. Outputs for dissemination". It includes a header with the DSPACE logo and navigation links. Below the title, there is a text area for describing activities and outputs. A table below lists example tasks and their descriptions:

Example task	Best example participation	Supercooperation for example	Great example event	Example title
Task	Process of cooperation, participation and working...	Process of cooperation, participation and working...	Event / Interaction	Publication

This screenshot shows a form titled "External conditions and requirements". It includes a header with the DSPACE logo and navigation links. Below the title, there is a text area for reflecting on external conditions and requirements. The form includes several sections:

- Title**: A text input field.
- Type of condition/requirement**: Radio buttons for Property rights of others, Legal conditions, Social and cultural conditions, Ecological conditions, and Technical and infrastructural conditions.
- Description and Reflection**: A text area for describing the condition and reflecting on its impact.
- Date from which the framework condition have an effect**: A date input field.
- Identification of influence**: Radio buttons for Strongly supporting, Slightly supporting, Both facilitating and hampering, Slightly hampering, and Strongly hampering.

Working Plan – structure items, add times and responsibilities

The screenshot shows the DSPACE Working Plan interface. At the top, the DSPACE logo and navigation links are visible. The main content area displays a list of tasks on the left and a Gantt chart on the right. The Gantt chart shows a timeline from January to January of the following year, with green bars representing task durations. The tasks are as follows:

Task Name	Type	Start Date	End Date	Organisations	Status
Vorarbeiten Lorem Ipsum dolor sit amet Forschungsvorhaben invidunt ut labore et dolore magna	Workpackage	23.03.2021	24.03.2021	Bundesminist, 4Science, Uni Kassel	not done yet
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam	Entity	23.03.2021	24.03.2021	Bundesminist, 4Science, Uni Kassel	not done yet
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam	Entity	23.03.2021	24.03.2021	Bundesminist, 4Science, Uni Kassel	not done yet
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna	Milestone	23.03.2021	24.03.2021	Bundesminist, 4Science, Uni Kassel	not done yet
Anforderung der Forschungsförderer, Erprobung für das Monitoring in Forschungsprozessen	Task	23.03.2021	24.03.2021	Bundesminist, 4Science, Uni Kassel	not done yet
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna	Task				not done yet

All development will be Open Source!

**Interest & Questions
Please contact us!**

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<https://synsicris.de>